

Synthesis of Thiazolo (4, 5-d) Pyrimidines ; A New Class of CNS Depressants. Studies in 4-Aminothiazolines—XIII

AMRIK SINGH* and AVTAR SINGH UPPAL

Chemistry Department, Guru Nanak Dev University, Amritsar-143 005 (India)

Manuscript received 15 November 1976, revised 15 February 1978, accepted 7 July 1978

2-Acetylthio-3-aryl-4-ethoxymethyleneamino-5-cyano- Δ^4 -thiazolines(I) on reaction with primary aliphatic amines furnished 2-acetylthio-3-aryl-6-alkyl-7-iminothiazolo (4, 5-d) pyrimidines (III, $R_1 = CH_3, n$ -propyl). Thiazolo (4, 5-d) pyrimidines(III) when heated in water for 40 hours underwent Dimroth rearrangement to 2-acetylthio-3-aryl-7-alkylaminothiazolo (4, 5-d) pyrimidines(VII). Two derivatives of (III) were tested on rats and both of them have been found to depress Central Nervous System.

ETHOXYMETHYLENEAMINO compounds derived from *o*-aminonitriles have been widely used in the synthesis of condensed 4-amino and 3-substituted-4-iminopyrimidines¹⁻⁵. However, 2-acetylthio-3-aryl-4-ethoxymethyleneamino- Δ^4 -5-cyanothiazolines⁶ (I, $R = CN$) failed to give thiazolo (4, 5-d) pyrimidines (III, $R_1 = C_6H_5, n$ -propyl) on reaction with aniline. Although reaction with ammonia did yield the expected 2-acetylthio-3-aryl-7-aminothiazolo (4, 5-d) pyrimidines(IV) smoothly in ethanol⁶. The reaction of I($R = CN$) with aniline afforded *N,N'*-diphenylformamide(V) and 2-acetylthio-3-aryl-4-amino-5-cyanothiazolines(VI, $R = CN$)⁷. The failure of formation of (III) with aniline has been attributed to an attack by another molecule of aniline leading to its (II, $R_1 = Ph$) splitting. However, when ($R_1 = H$), because of greater nucleophilic character of Nitrogen (*) of amidine (II), it underwent rapid intramolecular cyclisation to(IV) before splitting could occur. The ester (I, $R = COOC_2H_5, Ar = o$ -tolyl) failed to give thiazolo (4, 5-d) pyrimidine (IX, $R_1 = Ph$) even with ammonia and here also derivative of (VI, $R = COOC_2H_5$)⁸ was obtained. The aim of present investigation is to study the reaction of primary aliphatic amines with ethoxymethylene amino compounds (I, $R = CN$) and to see whether they behave like ammonia or aniline.

The reaction of I' aliphatic amines (methyl amine and *n*-propyl amine) and I($R = CN$) occurred at room temperature and the products obtained were 2-acetylthio-3-aryl-7-imino-6-alkylthiazolo (4, 5-d) pyrimidines (III, $R_1 = CH_3, n$ -propyl).

Dimroth rearrangement was successfully attempted on two derivatives (III, $R_1 = CH_3, n$ - C_3H_7) by heating in water for 40 hours and the products were 2-acetylthio-3-aryl-7-alkylaminothiazolo(4, 5-d) pyrimidines(VII, $R_1 = CH_3, n$ - C_3H_7).

The reaction of ester (I) ($Ar = o$ -tolyl, $R = COOC_2H_5$) with methyl amine as well as with

n-propyl amine failed to give the corresponding thiazolo (4, 5-d) pyrimidine (IX) or its precursor amidine (II, $R = COOC_2H_5$). 2-Acetylthio-3-*o*-tolyl-4-amino-5-carbomethoxythiazoline was however isolated as observed earlier in the reaction of I($R = COOC_2H_5$) with ammonia.

The structure of products (III) and (VII) is adequately supported by n.m.r. spectra. The n.m.r. spectra of (III, $Ar = o$ -tolyl, $R_1 = n$ - C_3H_7) run in $CDCl_3$ (TMS) as internal reference) possessed signals

at δ 1.0(3H, t, $J=7$ Hz), δ 1.62 (2H, sextet, $J=7$ Hz), δ 2.1 (3H, s), δ 2.2(3H, s), δ 3.95(3H, diffused triplet-NCH₃+1NH), δ 7.4(m, 4H aromatic), δ 7.66(1H, s, CH=N).

The n.m.r. spectra of VII(Ar=*o*-tolyl, R=*n*-C₃H₇) in CDCl₃ possessed the following signals at δ 1.0 (t, 3H, $J=7$ Hz), δ 1.75 broad multiplet (3H, NH+CH₃) which changes to a sextet (2H, $J=7$ Hz) after exchange with D₂O, δ 2.12(s, 3H, CH₃), δ 2.22 (3H, s, CH₃), δ 3.57 (multiplet, 2H, CH₂-N) this signal changes into a triplet after exchange with D₂O, δ 7.35 (m, 4H, aromatic) and δ 8.32 (s, H, CH=N-). The changes in the pattern of two sets of methylene protons clearly indicates that thiazolo (4, 5-d) pyrimidines exists as(VII) and not in the tautomeric form(VIII). The evidence for aromatic proton in pyrimidine (VII) is also available in the down field shift of CH=N as compared with the corresponding proton in (III). In the i.r. spectra of (VII) the CO str. frequency appeared on lower frequency side, i. e., ν max 1600 cm⁻¹. In the i. r. spectra of (III, Ar=*o*-tolyl, R₁=*n*-propyl) the NH, str appeared at 3350 and CO str at 1630 cm⁻¹.

Two of the derivatives of (III) (R=CH₃, Ar=*o*-tolyl, *p*-tolyl) were injected into albino rats in the form of aq. solutions of hydrochlorides and both of these compounds were found to depress central nervous system. It may be pointed out that thiazolo (4, 5-d) pyrimidines reported in literature have been found to possess various types of other biological activity but not the CNS depressant⁸⁻¹¹.

Experimental

2-Acetylimino-3-aryl-7-imino-6-n-propylthiazolo (4, 5-d) pyrimidines(III) (R₁=n-propyl) :

Appropriate 4-ethoxymethyleneamino- Δ^4 -thiazoline (I, R=CN) (2 g) was taken up in ethanol (10 ml) and *n*-propylamine (.5 ml) was added. The contents were shaken vigorously, an exothermic reaction was set in immediately and thiazolo (4, 5-d) pyrimidine (III, R₁=*n*-propyl) separated out. It was cooled, filtered and washed with ethanol. The product was found to be contaminated with 2-acetylimino-3-aryl-4-amino-5-cyano- Δ^4 -thiazoline(VI). The crude

product was taken up in the chloroform when thiazolo (4, 5-d) pyrimidine dissolved and 2-acetylimino-3-aryl-4-amino-5-cyano- Δ^4 -thiazoline (VI, R=CN) remained in suspension. It was filtered and the filtrate was evaporated to dryness (Yield 60-70%). The product was further purified by crystallization from ethanol.

2-Acetylimino-3-aryl-7-imino-6-methylthiazolo(4,5-d) pyrimidine (III, R₁=CH₃) :

4-Ethoxymethylene amino- Δ^4 thiazoline (I, R=CN) (2 g) was taken up in ethanol (10 ml) and dry methyl amine gas was passed for 5 minutes. The reaction occurred exothermically and the product obtained was worked up as above, yield (70-80%). Various derivatives of (III, R₁=CH₃, *n*-propyl) synthesized are listed in Table I.

2-Acetylimino-3-aryl-7-propylamino-thiazolo (4,5-d) pyrimidine(VII, R₁=n-propyl) :

Thiazolopyrimidine(III, R₁=*n*-propyl) was heated in water on a steam bath for 40 hours when it rearranged to (VII). The product was recrystallized from ethanol.

The derivatives of (VII) synthesized are listed in Table I.

2-Acetylimino-3-o-tolyl-4-amino-5-carbethoxy- Δ^4 -thiazoline(VI, Ar=o-tolyl, R=COOC₂H₅) :

Ethoxymethylene amino- Δ^4 -thiazoline (I, Ar=*o*-tolyl, R=COOC₂H₅) (2 g) was taken up in ethanol and was allowed to react with *n*-propyl amine or methyl amine as mentioned above, the reaction occurred immediately but the product in each case was (VI, Ar=*o*-tolyl, R=COOC₂H₅)⁶ and not the expected 2-acetylimino-3-aryl-6-phenylthiazolo (4, 5-d) pyrimidine-7-one. (IX, R₁=Ph).

TABLE I—THIAZOLO (4, 5-d) PYRIMIDINES

Compound No.	Structure	Ar	R ₁	M.P. °C	Found			M. F.	Required		
					C	H	N		C	H	N
1.	III	Phenyl	Methyl	240	—	—	22.95	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N ₃ OS	—	—	23.41
2.	III	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	Methyl	230	—	—	22.15	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₃ OS	—	—	22.36
3.	III	Phenyl	<i>n</i> -Propyl	240	—	—	21.3	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₃ OS	—	—	21.40
4.	III	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	<i>n</i> -Propyl	227	59.47	6.00	20.88	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ N ₃ OS	59.82	5.57	20.52
5.	III	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	<i>n</i> -Propyl	225	—	—	20.82	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ N ₃ OS	—	—	20.52
6.	VII	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	<i>n</i> -Propyl	227	59.65	5.53	20.64	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ N ₃ OS	59.82	5.57	20.52
7.	VII	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	<i>n</i> -Propyl	195	—	—	20.22	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ N ₃ OS	—	—	20.52

n. m. r. spectra of (III, R₁=CH₃, Ar=*p*-tolyl) run in CDCl₃, possessed signals at δ 2.2 (s, 3H, CH₃), δ 2.42 (s, 3H, CH₃), δ 3.5 (s, 3H, CH₃), δ 3.75-4.25 (m, 1H, NH exchanged with D₂O), δ 7.01 to 7.4 (m, 4H, aromatic), and δ 7.72 (s, 1H, -OH=N)

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to U.G.C. for financial assistance and to Dr. (Mrs.) Harjit Kaur Mangat and Miss Charanjit Kaur of Biology Deptt., Guru Nanak Dev University, Amritsar for testing the compounds on Rats.

References

1. G. SHAW and D. N. BUTLER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 4040.
2. E. C. TAYLOR and A. MCKILLOP, *Advances in Organic Chemistry*, 1960, 7, 238.
3. A. ALBERT, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin I*, 1973, 2659.
4. A. ALBERT, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin I*, 1973, 1634.
5. E. C. TAYLOR and J. G. BERGER, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1967, 32, 2376.
6. A. SINGH and A. S. UPPAL, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976, 14B, 728.
7. A. SINGH and A. S. UPPAL, *Indian J. Chem.* 1978, 16B, 779.
8. A. MAGGIALO and H. G. HITCHING, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 81, 4226.
9. E. F. SCHROEDER and R. M. DODSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 84, 1904.
10. E. F. SCHROEDER (To G. D. Searle and Co.) U. S. 3277093, Aug., 3, 1965.
11. M. HORIUCHI, *Chem. and Pharm Bull. Japan*, 62, 7480.